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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DENTISTRY (LITERATE REVIEW)**Khusainboev J.D.**

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Resume. Artificial intelligence is a quickly developing technology that is being incorporated into modern humans' life more and more. The field of dentistry is one of its most promising uses. Artificial intelligence can be used to increase the efficacy of oral disease diagnosis, treatment, and prevention thanks to modern technology. Artificial intelligence in dentistry makes it possible for dentists to work more accurately and effectively. Additionally, it speeds up therapy, increases patient comfort, and enhances the overall quality of the patient experience. The uses, benefits, and drawbacks of artificial intelligence were discussed in this article. Techniques and tools for improving the processes of diagnosis, treatment, and prevention were examined. The healthcare system can undergo a significant transformation thanks to new technologies. In order to maximize outcomes in the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of oral illnesses, artificial intelligence will eventually play a crucial role in dental practice.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, dental care, preventive, diagnostics, and advances.

СТОМАТОЛОГИЯДА СУНЪИЙ ИДРОКНИ ҚЎЛЛАШ (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРҲИ)**Хусаинбоев Ж.Д.**

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Резюме. Сунъий идрок (СИ) — бу замонавий инсон ҳаётига тобора кўпроқ кириб бораётган, тез ривожланаётган технологиядир. Стоматология соҳаси унинг энг истиқболли қўлланиш йўналишларидан биридир. Замонавий технологиялар туфайли сунъий идрок оғиз бўшлиғи касалликларини ташихлаш, даволаш ва олдини олиш самарадорлигини ошириш учун ишлатилиши мумкин. Стоматологиядаги сунъий идрок шифокорларга янада аниқ ва самарали ишлаш имконини беради. Бундан ташқари, у даволашни тезлаштиради, беморларнинг қулайлигини оширади ва умумий бемор тажрибасининг сифатини яхшилайдди. Ушбу мақолада сунъий идрокнинг қўллаш соҳалари, афзалликлари ва камчиликлари муҳокама қилинди. Ташихлаш, даволаш ва олдини олиш жараёнларини такомиллаштириш усуллари ва воситалари кўриб чиқилди. Янги технологиялар соғлиқни сақлаш тизимини сезиларли даражада ўзгартириши мумкин. Охир-оқибат, сунъий идрок оғиз бўшлиғи касалликларини ташихлаш, даволаш ва олдини олишда энг юқори натижаларга эришиш учун стоматологик амалиётда ҳал қилувчи рол ўйнайдди.

Калит сўзлар: сунъий идрок, стоматологик ёрдам, профилактика, диагностика, ютуқлар.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В СТОМАТОЛОГИИ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)**Хусаинбоев Ж.Д.**

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Резюме. Искусственный интеллект (ИИ) — это быстро развивающаяся технология, которая все шире внедряется в жизнь современного человека. Сфера стоматологии является одним из самых многообещающих направлений его применения. Современные технологии позволяют использовать искусственный интеллект для повышения эффективности диагностики, лечения и профилактики заболеваний полости рта. Искусственный интеллект в стоматологии дает врачам возможность работать более точно и результативно. Кроме того, он ускоряет терапию, повышает комфорт пациентов и улучшает общее качество обслуживания. В данной статье рассматриваются области применения, преимущества и недостатки искусственного интеллекта. Были изучены методы и инструменты для совершенствования процессов диагностики, лечения и профилактики. Новые технологии могут значительно преобразовать систему здравоохранения. В конечном итоге искусственный интеллект будет играть решающую роль в стоматологической практике для максимизации результатов в диагностике, лечении и профилактике заболеваний полости рта.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, стоматологическая помощь, профилактика, диагностика, достижения.

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Introduction. Modern medicine is becoming more inventive and technologically advanced every day. Accordingly, artificial intelligence (AI) is being used more and more in various facets of medical practice. One such field where AI has already been used is dentistry. AI can be used to increase the efficacy of oral disease diagnosis, treatment, and prevention thanks to modern technologies. The use of AI in dentistry will be discussed in this article along with its benefits, drawbacks, and capabilities.

1. An Overview of Artificial Intelligence's Use in Dentistry One of the most exciting fields of medical research is artificial intelligence [1]. AI in dentistry has the potential to enhance oral disease detection, management, and prevention. Let's examine AI's potential applications in dentistry in more detail.

Diagnosis First, let's examine how artificial intelligence is used to diagnose oral illnesses. The two most prevalent conditions are periodontitis and tooth decay. Oral illnesses are diagnosed through radiographic examinations and visual assessment. However, radiological examinations can be detrimental to the patient's health, and visual assessment does not always provide an appropriate assessment of the disease's presence and severity. AI can be quite beneficial in this situation.

Image analysis is one way AI is being used to diagnose oral diseases. Meanwhile, X-rays and photos of teeth and gums are analyzed by AI [2], [3]. Cavities, periodontal disease, and other oral diseases can be reliably detected using neural networks that have been trained on vast volumes of data.

"Caries Diagnosis" by Dental Monitoring is one initiative that uses AI in dentistry. This study employs artificial intelligence to identify cavities in a dental image. Patients receive a precise diagnosis and treatment suggestions based on the data gathered from the analysis.

Treatment AI has the potential to enhance the efficacy of oral disease treatment in addition to diagnostics. AI can be used, for instance, to identify the best plan of action for treating periodontitis, which will be most successful for each patient. The development of personalized implants and prostheses is another instance of how AI is being used to treat oral diseases. AI has the potential to produce implants and prostheses that are precisely customized for every patient, taking into consideration their unique demands and anatomical characteristics [4]. NextDent's "3D Printing of Teeth" project is an illustration of this type of technology [5]. In this study, precise 3D representations of a patient's teeth and gums are produced using artificial intelligence. Custom implants and prosthetics are made using these models, guaranteeing the patient the utmost comfort and accuracy [2, 4, 6]. 2.1.3. Prevention AI can be used to prevent oral disorders in addition to diagnosing and treating them. AI, for instance, can be used to create individualized preventative plans for every patient, accounting for their food preferences, lifestyle, and anatomical characteristics.

Oral-B's "Smart Toothbrush" project is an illustration of this type of technology. This research uses artificial intelligence (AI) to create a customized dental care program by analyzing a patient's food and lifestyle choices. A customized oral health evaluation and treatment recommendations are given to each patient.

Therefore, AI in dentistry has the potential to greatly increase the efficacy of oral disease detection, treatment, and prevention. AI may be used to establish individualized prevention programs, identify the best course of therapy, and make unique implants and prostheses. In conclusion, it should be highlighted that there is a great deal of promise for raising the standard of healthcare through the application of AI in dentistry. AI can be used to prevent oral disorders, identify the best course of therapy, and increase the accuracy of diagnostics [6]. AI also enables the development of personalized implants and prostheses that take into consideration the anatomical characteristics of individuals [2]. Even though artificial intelligence (AI) in dentistry is still a relatively new topic, numerous initiatives and technologies are currently effectively utilizing AI in dental practice. AI will probably play a significant role in dentistry in the future, enabling the best possible outcomes in the prevention and treatment of oral illnesses.

Characteristics of Dental Artificial Intelligence Applications. There are benefits and drawbacks of using AI in dentistry. We will look at the primary ones in this chapter. Benefits of AI in dentistry include: - Improved diagnostic precision: AI makes it possible to diagnose oral disorders with a high degree of accuracy. - optimizing the course of treatment: AI can assist dentists in deciding on the best course of treatment for a patient based on medical data and information about the outcomes of prior treatments. AI can also analyze data using machine learning algorithms [7, p. 97] and examine large volumes of information to detect pathologies that might be missed during a standard visual assessment. This permits the creation of customized prevention programs: AI makes it possible to create customized oral disease prevention programs for every patient, taking into consideration their unique needs and anatomical characteristics. AI may identify illness risks and recommend individualized preventive measures through the application of machine learning algorithms [7] and medical data analysis; - developing bespoke implants and prosthetics: AI can be utilized to develop custom implants and prostheses. AI is capable of producing implants and prosthetics that closely match a patient's physical traits through the use of 3D modeling and medical data processing [2]. The high cost of the technology and the requirement for extensive and intricate staff training may be the main reasons

for the limited use of AI in dentistry. Other drawbacks include: - Limited access to technology: One of the primary obstacles to the use of AI in dentistry is the lack of access to the right technology. Artificial intelligence is a costly technology that needs to be developed and implemented by qualified specialists and with a large financial commitment. However, the broader acceptance and application of AI in dentistry is becoming feasible due to technological advancements and the introduction of new financing sources. The possibility of errors is another drawback of utilizing AI in dentistry. For instance, some businesses provide solutions that let dental offices employ AI technology without having to buy their own computer power and software.

AI is not perfect, even though it can process vast amounts of data and make judgments based on its analysis. Furthermore, because AI relies on algorithms that might not take into consideration every case, mistakes may occur; insufficient data is another barrier to the application of AI in dentistry. AI requires a substantial amount of data for analysis in order to function properly.

However, there might not be enough data in some dental specialties to train AI; employing AI in dentistry also necessitates skilled professionals who can handle data and use the right tools; and ethical and legal concerns are also brought up by the use of AI in dentistry.

The usage of AI, for instance, carries the risk of lowering the standard of healthcare for those without access to this technology. Potential problems with data security and patient privacy also exist. Furthermore, there is a chance that AI will eventually replace people. Dentists and dental hygienists may become less important as a result, which could have a detrimental effect on their professional development. In summary, there are numerous benefits to using AI in dentistry that can enhance the standard of oral disease detection, management, and prevention. This entails task automation, cutting down on data processing time, and lowering the possibility of mistakes.

Nevertheless, the application of AI technology in dentistry is not without its restrictions. One of the primary drawbacks is that AI algorithms need a lot of data to be trained and optimized, which might cause issues in small clinics.

Additionally, experts' work cannot be entirely replaced by AI technology, and accurate result interpretation necessitates a certain amount of expertise and training. However, there will be substantial advantages to dentistry from the application of AI. AI technologies have the potential to improve the efficiency and time-saving aspects of dentists' job while also improving patient access to higher-quality care. Thus, it can be said that the application of AI in dentistry has a great deal of promise to enhance people's health and quality of life, notwithstanding certain drawbacks.

The Potential of Artificial Intelligence in Dentistry Robotizing dental procedures can assist physicians in performing tedious and time-consuming procedures including obtaining impressions, placing implants, and treating root canals. For instance, implant placement and other surgical procedures are performed using the Yomi robotic dental system. Yomi assists dentists in precisely locating implants and placing them by utilizing AI navigation technology. The automation of the root canal procedure is another possible application of robotics in dentistry. Because of their complexity, root canals can be difficult for dentists to treat. On the other hand, AI-based robotic systems are capable of processing data automatically and accurately determining the channel's width and depth [2]. Teledentistry is another area in which artificial intelligence is being applied in dentistry. A new approach to dental care called teledentistry enables patients to get diagnosis and consultations without physically visiting a facility. AI can be used to develop teledentistry systems that can evaluate patient data and provide a diagnosis. All things considered, the automation of repetitive procedures, treatment process optimization, and diagnostic enhancement are all connected to the future of AI application in dentistry. The standard of medical care will rise, and physicians' precision and effectiveness will rise as well. But it's also important to take into account the drawbacks of some algorithms' poor accuracy as well as concerns about patient data security and privacy.

Robots can also help with dental operations that need a high level of precision. Robotic devices, for instance, can be utilized for orthodontic operations, dental implants, and planning [9], [10]. This can enhance procedural results and lower the possibility of human error. But even with the apparent benefits, there are drawbacks to automating dental procedures. For instance, purchasing and maintaining a robot might be highly expensive. Furthermore, adequate procedural control may occasionally necessitate the presence of a human operator, which could result in higher personnel expenditures.

All things considered, robotics and AI in dentistry have a promising future. Doctors will be able to detect and treat illnesses more precisely, make fewer mistakes, and enhance procedural results thanks to new technologies.

Nevertheless, in order to reduce patient risks and adhere to legal requirements, it is vital to take into account the limitations and carefully deploy new technology.

Conclusion Several studies and real-world uses of AI technologies in dentistry were examined throughout the evaluation of AI utilization in this medical specialty. AI in dentistry has been found to have the following benefits: - increased precision in the diagnosis of oral and dental conditions; - enhanced treatment quality and error prevention; - decreased treatment time and expense; - optimized dental clinic operations and enhanced patient care; - decreased workload for physicians and increased their productivity.

But there are also drawbacks to utilizing AI in dentistry, including restricted access to technology, the requirement for a lot of data to train algorithms, and the possibility of misinterpreting data and abusing AI during treatment.

The application of AI in dentistry offers enormous potential to enhance the standard of medical care and streamline dental clinic operations, notwithstanding several drawbacks. Key avenues for the advancement of AI technology in dentistry include the automation of dental procedures, automated diagnostics, and forecasting.

But in order for AI to become more common in dentistry, a number of crucial issues must be resolved, including establishing a standardized approach to data collection and processing, establishing guidelines and standards for the application of AI technologies, and making these technologies more accessible to small and medium-sized dental offices. Their accessibility and usability will be considerably more beneficial and contribute to the efficiency and accessibility of healthcare.

All things considered, the application of AI in dentistry holds enormous promise for raising treatment standards and streamlining dental clinic operations. To safeguard patient privacy and avoid mistakes in diagnosis and treatment, it is vital to take into account the risks and limitations of these technologies.

Future advancements in AI and robotics technology should result in even faster and more precise patient diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation. They should also optimize dental clinic management procedures and lower healthcare expenses [6].

AI will be a tool in the job of specialists rather than a replacement for physicians, despite all of its benefits.

Conclusion: Optimizing dental clinic operations and providing the best possible patient care can be achieved by combining technology with human expertise and intuition. Consequently, the application of AI in dentistry is currently producing

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